

Supplementary Material of Empowering Users toward Environmentally Sustainable Digital Practices: From Web-Based to Generative AI Interactions

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1 Web Extensions Comparison

Table 1 shows the difference of Carbon Tracker compared to other existing web extensions.

Table 1: A table summarising the differences between the tool described in the manuscript (i.e., Carbon Tracker) and those previously available.

	CarbonTracker (our tool)	ChatGPT Carbon Tracker ¹	Carbon- Calculator ¹	GPTFootprint [7]
<i>Web Carbon Emissions Measurement</i>	✓	✗	✓	✗
<i>ChatGPT Carbon Emissions Measurement</i>	✓	✓	✗	✓
<i>Cumulative Carbon Emissions</i>	✓	✗	✗	✗
<i>Carbon Emissions Visualisation</i>	✓	✗	✗	✗
<i>Carbon Emissions Translation</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Limit Your Usage</i>	✓	✗	✗	✓
<i>Usage Analytics</i>	✓	✗	✗	✗
<i>Export function</i>	✓	✗	✗	✓

2 Questionnaires

2.1 Pre-evaluation Questionnaire

Previous Competencies in AI Between square brackets are the possible answers. A 7-item Likert scale was applied. The questions were based on previous questionnaire by [9].

- How would you describe your feelings about the overall impact of technology on society? [Likert]
- Have you ever heard the term artificial intelligence or AI? [Yes / No]
- Can you explain what the term Artificial Intelligence (AI) means? [I can explain well what is meant by that / I know roughly what it means, but it is difficult to explain / I don't know what it means]

- To the best of your knowledge, does your institution use Artificial Intelligence (AI)? [Yes / No / Don't know]
- Which of these statements best describes your interaction with AI at work? [I work with AI / I manage workers who work with AI / I develop/maintain AI / I interact with AI in another way / I have no interaction with AI at work / Don't know]
- How likely do you think it is that you will work with AI or interact with it in any other way in your job in the next 10 years? [Very likely / Somewhat likely/ Neither likely nor unlikely / Somewhat unlikely / Very unlikely]
- If you have experience of interacting with AI, could you please provide more information? Please share as much as you possible. [Open-ended]

Environmental Sustainability

Self-Efficacy (SE), Action Effectiveness (AE) [5]

See the supplemental material of the Giudici et al. [5] paper, available at [6].

New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) [4]

See the re-adapted questionnaire by Anderson et al. [1].

2.2 Post-evaluation Questionnaire

User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) [8]

See the abbreviated version of the questionnaire at <https://www.ueq-online.org/>.

System Usability Scale (SUS) [3]

See the items of the questionnaire at [2].

Additionally, the *Post-evaluation Questionnaire* includes also the items from the *Environmental Sustainability* of the *Pre-evaluation Questionnaire* (i.e., Section 2.1). Finally, the following two open-ended questions were required: “How was your experience with the system in general? Did you find anything in particular that fascinated or intrigued you?” and “Any other things you would like to add?”.

3 Tasks

The tasks' brief is summarised below. When additional documents were requested to perform tasks, these were provided to participants via a shared folder, available at <https://bit.ly/46UbiNI>.

- **Task 1.** Write an email (newsletter style) to announce the following event within your organization.
- **Task 2.** Summarise and extract the key points of the following presentation (in a bullet point list).
- **Task 3.** Reply to an email on a particular request of a student (the text of the email was written in a foreign language for the participant).
- **Task 4.** You are asked to write a document to promote internally (within your organization) on the organization of a staff week on a topic of your interest.

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